

Photonic Based Marine Radar Demonstrator: from the laboratory characterization to the field trial demonstration

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Abstract— This paper presents the results obtained during the field trial experiments of the first photonic-based radar system demonstrator, in a real maritime environment. The developed demonstrator exploits photonic technologies for both the generation and the detection of radar RF signals, allowing increased performance even in term of system flexibility. The photonic radar performance have been compared with a state of the art commercial system for maritime applications provided by GEM elettronica resorting to ad-hoc laboratory tests which show comparable results in term of pre and post detection capability. Moreover, to further validate the effectiveness of the implemented architecture, comparison trials of the two radar systems have also been presented in an operative scenario with non cooperative targets in the area of San Bendetto del Tronto port (Italy).

Keywords—radar system; microwave photonics.

I. INTRODUCTION

Radar systems have known impressive advances throughout their long history, pushing electronics to a relentless progress [1]. On the other hand, novel and higher-performance electronic devices and subsystems have driven the development of new radar architectures and functionalities, allowing the realization of very sophisticated remote sensing systems [2]. However, while software solutions can still bring about substantial room for improvements, electronics is nowadays approaching its theoretical and practical limits in terms of performance, miniaturization, power consumption and cost reduction.

Radar history has witnessed a gradual and continuous migration from analog to digital systems. The digital approach has by now penetrated all the radar architecture layers, leading to the paradigms of software-defined radar (SDR) and cognitive radar [3]. The development of SDR has given a preeminent role to processing in remote sensing systems, allowing to mitigate undesired phenomena such as unwanted echoes, propagation impairments, distortions and noise introduced by the electronic devices employed in signal

transmission and reception. Indeed, electronic subsystems can guarantee high performance over a given bandwidth and, as a rule of thumb, increasing the frequency worsens performance. In the last two decades, a considerable effort has been spent to realize high-performance microwave and millimeterwave devices and, in some cases, photonic technologies have profitably been exploited to this aim [4], [5], [6]. In particular, photonics perfectly fits with the SDR approach and, thanks to its inherent extremely broad bandwidth, total immunity to electromagnetic interferences, and low weight and size [6], can represent an enabling technology allowing to overcome some of the main limitations of electronics [7]. In detail, optical signal sources, such as mode-locked lasers (MLLs), can help in the implementation of ultra-stable, widely tunable micro- and millimeter wave oscillators [8][9][10]. On the other hand, exploiting the same optical source in the receiver side, it is possible the realization of a photonics-assisted analog-to-digital converter (ADC) directly in the radio frequency (RF) domain, with superior performance with respect to traditional electronic ADCs [11][12].

In this paper, we consider the photonic fully-digital coherent radar recently developed within the PHODIR project [13][14] and we further investigate its performance in details. In particular, here we mean to address one of the fundamental issues raised by the presentation of the photonics-based radar [7]: the actual performance of our system, compared with a state-of-the-art, commercial radar system. The comparison shows the high performance of our radar, which are slightly under the reference top-class product SeaEagle [15], provided by GEM elettronica for this activity. As will be shown in detail throughout the paper, the outcomes of the comparison definitely prove the effectiveness of the photonics-assisted architecture, which is endowed with complete frequency and waveform agility. For this reason, it can also be transparent to any remote sensing application, thus providing a photonic “core block” which, connected to a proper front-end, can fulfil any remote sensing function. Finally, our system has been conceived and realized employing commercial photonic and

optoelectronic devices, which are typically adopted for communication purposes. We firmly believe that the development of ad-hoc designed devices, optimized for radar applications, can significantly improve the performance of the photonics-assisted radar. Furthermore, recent and forthcoming advances in photonic integration are very promising in the perspective of realizing a new generation of extremely high

frequency $f_0 = Nf_{rep} + IF$ where N represents the inter mode spacing. Furthermore the intrinsic locking condition of each laser mode guarantees that the generated signal present a good level of phase stability even for large mode's separation, and consequently high carrier frequency.

The same MLL can be used in order to implement the optical sampling of the received echo signal directly in the RF

Fig. 1. Scheme of principle of the generation (A) and reception (B) process of the radar RF signal. IF: Intermediate frequency; PD: Photodiode; ADC: Analog-to-Digital Converter; BF: Microwave filter bandwidth; BPD: Photodiode electrical bandwidth; BADC: ADC analog bandwidth

performance, low cost, compact and future-proof photonics-assisted radars.

The paper is organized as follows. Section II-A introduces the principle of operation of the photonics-aided transceiver, with main emphasis on the signal generation and detection. Section II-B describes the implementation of the radar demonstrator with its complete characterization. Finally, in Section III the experimental results of the photonic radar are presented with a direct comparison between the plan position indicator (PPI) plots provided by our photonic radar and by the reference system from GEM *elettronica*.

II. PHOTONIC RADAR SYSTEM

A. Principle of operation

In the proposed photonics-assisted transceiver a single MLL is employed to generate and detect RF signals at any desired frequency with the peculiarity of avoiding multiple mixing processes with different local oscillators. A basic scheme, useful to understand the photonic generation and detection process, is depicted in Fig.1. In detail, Fig.1-A represents the generation of the RF radar signal. The desired radar waveform is digitally generated at a low intermediate frequency (IF) and fed into the electrical port of an electro optical modulator. This signal modulates the amplitude of the MLL source used as reference carrier generator. Since the optical spectrum of the MLL is composed by a set of lines spaced by the repetition frequency f_{rep} , the resulting modulated frequency content is represented by an optical combination of modes with sidebands at a distance equal to the IF of the radar signal. Then, the photodetector (PD) produces the beating of all these spectral components and finally, a bandpass RF filter with bandwidth B_F selects the signal to be transmitted at a

domain (Fig.1-B). In the optical frequency domain, the sampling process corresponds to the generation of replicas of the detected signal spectrum as sidebands of the MLL modes. The modulated pulses are then sent into a PD with an electrical bandwidth B_{PD} , and the photodetection process performs the down-conversion of the echo from the RF carrier frequency f_0 back to the original IF (Fig.1-B, bottom). Just as in the generation process, here no electrical mixers are used as well. The employed ADC, with an analog bandwidth B_{ADC} , eventually digitizes the signals after the down-conversions to IF.

B. Demonstrator description

Since the electronic front end of the PHODIR radar has been developed using commercial, narrow bandwidth devices, its operative frequency is limited within the X-band with a nominal RF carrier of 9900MHz and a maximum agility and instantaneous bandwidth of 40MHz. As sketched in Fig. 2, the photonic core is composed by three modules: the laser module, the photonic transmitter, and the receiver module. The laser module contains the semiconductor passive MLL and the locking circuit to phase lock the laser source to a reference oscillator that serves as the master reference for the whole system. The employed MLL presents a pulse length of 1ps and a repetition rate of 400MHz. The laser output is handed to the other two sub-systems: the photonic transmitter and receiver modules. In the transmitter module the optical pulses are amplified and filtered to provide sufficient optical power to the optical Mach-Zehnder modulator (MZM) and to reject the amplifier noise. The MZM is driven by a direct digital synthesizer (DDS) that generates the desired radar waveform at a low IF, equal to 100MHz. The DDS is embedded in the controller module, and it has a nominal resolution of 16 bits at a sampling rate of 400MSps, with an analog bandwidth (BW)

of 160MHz. The modulated optical signal is then detected by a 12GHz-bandwidth PD producing all the signal beatings in its electrical bandwidth. Then a band-pass filter centered at 9900MHz with a BW of 40MHz extracts the desired RF signal. Furthermore, a low noise amplifier compensates for the conversion losses induced by the optical up-conversion process, reaching an output peak power of about -30dBm

Fig. 2. Picture of the developed photonic radar system, represented with the antenna provided by GEM elettronica s.r.l. for this work

The RF transmitter chain is composed by a cascade of a driver amplifier and a high power amplifier (a travelling-wave tube) with a saturation power level of about 53dBm. Additional pin diode switches have also been added to increase the isolation of the RF circulator. The employed antenna is a 6-feet slotted waveguide array with a central frequency of 9.9GHz, an horizontal and vertical beam width of about 1° and 25° respectively, a gain of 30dB, and a rotation speed of about 27 rounds per minute. The whole antenna system has been provided by GEM elettronica. At the receiver, the RF front end is composed by a cascade of low noise amplification stages with a total noise figure (NF) of about 8dB and a total amplification of about 100dB. In addition, a sensitive time control (STC) has been used to compensate the fading due to the two-way propagation. After the RF front end, the radar signal is optically sampled modulating the MLL pulses in a MZM with an electro-optical BW of 20GHz, then a 2GHz-BW PD transforms the optical samples into the electrical signal directly down-converted in the first Nyquist region. Finally, a low-speed high-precision ADC brings out the digital samples for the radar processor. The ADC has an effective precision of 10bits and samples the incoming signal at 80MSps. The laboratory characterization of the radar receiver has been divided into two parts. The first one focuses on the pre-detection sensitivity, and is related to the hardware components within the receiver only, whereas the second one studies the post-detection sensitivity, and it is relative to the ability of the system to detect weak targets, also thanks to the digital signal

processing algorithms. To perform the predetection radar sensitivity an RF tone at the central frequency of the PHODIR radar is generated by means of a waveform generator. Then a variable attenuator is used to reduce the power level of the RF source, reaching the minimum level distinguishable from the radar demonstrator receiver with respect to the noise level. Since the RF source is set to 9.9GHz and the MLL repetition frequency is 400MHz, the down-converted signal appears as an IF at 100MHz (back-aliased 25 times) with the maximum bandwidth of the developed radar receiver (40MHz). Fig. 3-B depicts the down-converted signal acquired by means of an electrical spectrum analyzer with a span of 40MHz and a resolution bandwidth (RBW) of 1MHz.

Fig. 3 (A) Experimental scheme of the pre-detection radar sensitivity. (B) Downconverted electrical spectra of the test signal acquired by the electrical spectrum analyzer.

The minimum detectable signal (MDS) for the PHODIR system is defined as the minimum power level of the attenuated RF tone that guarantees a down-converted signal 3dB higher than the noise floor level. Integrating over the RBW, the MDS has been measured to be -106dBm, whereas the noise floor over the entire receiver bandwidth is -90dBm. Since the theoretical noise floor level for an ideal 40MHz-BW receiver is -98dBm, the total noise figure of the PHODIR radar receiver, i.e. considering the RF front-end cascaded by the photonic transceiver, can be estimated in 8dB. In Fig. 4-A, the scheme of the laboratory post detection measurement set up is depicted. The photonic transmitter generates a pulse compressed waveform (a linear chirp) which is delayed by means of an optical delay line to emulate the radar to target range; then, a RF variable attenuator emulates the round-trip attenuation and the signal is finally sent to the photonic radar receiver. The photonic receiver properly amplifies the signal prior to the down-conversion to the nominal IF, and finally the ADC keeps the digital samples useful for the DSP algorithms.

Fig. 4 (A) Experimental scheme of the post-detection radar sensitivity. (B) Radar range profile of an emulated weak target after the detection algorithms.

The result of the radar detection is shown in Fig. 4-B, where a stronger peak is clearly visible at a range of about 2.7km (equal to the delay line length), as a result of the

compression and integration processes. The dashed line in Fig. 4-B represents the 3dB level with respect to the normalized maximum value in dB scale. The RF input power at the photonic radar receiver is set to -118dBm, the pulsewidth (PW) and the pulse repetition frequency (PRF) are 5 μ sec and 10kHz, respectively, and the chirp frequency deviation is 2MHz. The receiver filter, whose BW is 2MHz, reduces the receiver in-band thermal noise. The theoretical time-bandwidth product is $B_{\text{chirp}}T_i=10$, whereas the compression gain is 10dB. Since the number of integrated pulses is around 125 (considering the waveform under test and a dwell time of 12.5ms), the integration gain is about 21dB. Therefore, the theoretical whole processing gain is about 31dB. As it can be seen from the Fig. 4Fig. -B, the detected peak is greater than the 3dB level imposed as a reference value for a correct detection.

Table 1 shows the main specifications of the PHODIR radar demonstrator compared with the SeaEagle radar provided by GEM *elettronica* company.

Table 1 Specifications of the PHODIR demonstrator, compared with the SEAEAGLE by GEM *elettronica*

Parameters	PHODIR	SEAEAGLE
Peak Power	50W (@ WR90)	100W (@ WR90)
RF frequency [MHz]	9880-9920 (continuous)	9300-9500 (step)
Max bandwidth	40MHz	40MHz
Noise figure	8dB	5.5dB
MDS	-87dBm@40MHz BW	-90dBm@40MHz BW
Processing gain	31dB @ $T_i=12.5\text{msec}$, PW=5 μ sec, B=2MHz, PRF=10KHz, ($G_c=21\text{dB}+G_r=10\text{dB}$)	Max 30dB @ PW=93 μ sec, B=10MHz (only compression gain)
Frequency accuracy	120ppm (13fsec)	100ppm (10fsec)
Max range	18NM (cargo target)	48NM (cargo target)
Pulsewidth	0.2-10 μ sec	50nsec-93 μ sec
PRF	1-12KHz	350-2500Hz
Modulation format	Any	Chirp

III. RESULTS

The PHODIR radar has been tested in cooperation with the company GEM *elettronica s.r.l.* in the area of the San Benedetto del Tronto port (Italy) in May 2014. At first, the field trial tests were carried out only with the photonic radar; later, the detections obtained by the PHODIR radar system have been compared to the detections of a flagship product developed by GEM *elettronica*, namely the SeaEagle radar [15].

Fig. 5-A reports an example of the PHODIR radar detection of the harbor area under test. In this particular set up, the transmitted waveform was a pulse train of PW = 1 μ sec and a pulse repetition interval (PRI) of 100 μ s, with a 40MHz linear chirp, for broadening the pulses bandwidth, thus reducing the range resolution (down to 3.75 meters). The transmitted power was about 50W (47dBm). The coherent integration time was set to 7.5msec including 75 radar pulses. In this case the integration gain was about 19dB (7.5msec of dwell time and 10KHz of PRF) and the compression gain about 16dB (1 μ sec

of PW and 40MHz of bandwidth) for a total processing gain of about 35dB.

Fig. 5 - (A) PHODIR radar detection of the San Benedetto del Tronto harbour area. (B) Range Doppler map of the detected target. Inset: range profile of the detected target.

In Fig. 5-A, the black dot represents the radar site (the GEM *elettronica* test range), whereas the gray circle identifies the blind region of the radar receiver, defined in order to prevent possible damages to the system's receiver due to strong echoes from close structures. The superposition of the port map and the PHODIR radar detection trace show both the coastal area and harbor shape are well represented. Furthermore the radar detection includes the echoes of the breakwater lines and of a small boat at a distance of about 0.42 nautical miles (NM) from the radar. Fig. 5-B represents the obtained range-Doppler map of the antenna angular sector in the direction of the moving target. A strong peak is clearly visible at the distance of 0.42NM, with a radial velocity of about 5knots. The inset shows a zoomed version of the range profile.

After this preliminary measurements the PHODIR radar has been tested simultaneously with the GEM *elettronica* SEAGLE radar. Fig. 6 depicts the comparison between the two radar systems, simultaneously detecting the same scene.

In Fig. 6-A the PPI plot of the SEA EAGLE radar is shown with a maximum displayed range of 12NM, where 5 different target detections are present, highlighted by small circles. On the other hand, Fig. 6-B represents the PPI plot obtained by the PHODIR radar over a maximum displayed range of 8NM. In this measurement, the transmitted waveform is a 10MHz-broad linear chirp over 3 μ sec-PW pulses, with PRF=10kHz.

These parameters have been chosen in order to obtain an energy budget (i.e. the total energy of the coherently integrated pulses) as similar as possible to the exploited SEA EAGLE configuration. The targets from 1 to 4 are detected from both the systems, whereas the target number 5 is present only in the GEM radar plot, since it is beyond the displayed range with respect to the PHODIR plot. The coastal area and harbor shape are well detected from both the systems.

Fig. 6 - Plan position indicator comparison of the GEM radar (A) and of the PHODIR radar (B).

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, after a brief discussion on the principle of operation, the PHODIR radar system demonstrator developed at the CNIT has been presented and detailed. The performance of the radar demonstrator have been evaluated and also compared with respect to a state-of-the-art, commercial coherent radar system (operating in the same frequency band),

provided by the Italian company GEM *elettronica* s.r.l. The laboratory tests show comparable performances of the PHODIR radar demonstrator, once more validating the potential suitability of photonic technologies to remote sensing applications. Furthermore, the issue of the localization of marine targets by a photonic radar system in harbor surveillance applications has also been addressed, within the area of San Benedetto del Tronto port. The PHODIR PPI plots, compared with real detection of the SEA EAGLE radar, show good detection performance of both marine vessels and coastal area. Although, in order to better exploit the benefits of the photonic technologies in remote sensing, especially in term of wide bandwidth and flexibility, further improvements are expected in the field of multifunctional photonic radar architecture.

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